

African Traditional Religious Values, Digitalization and Challenges in Contemporary Society

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Abstract

The cultural values of the Africans are reflection of their cultural heritage that presented and projected them as a people with unique and embracing socio-cultural values, which differentiated them from other culture and race around the world. African traditional religion is indigenous to the Africans, it is a religion that the Africans are born into and it's as old as the African continent. However, the religion has being greatly diminished by Christianity and Islam, as a result of their social acceptability. The cyber space is now leveraged on to heighten the campaign against indigenous religion, because the digital space is seriously tilted against it; more over digitalization has made the universe a small village. Despite the numerous contributions of digital technology to the development and promotion of Christian and Islamic values across Africa continent. Sadly, it has being manipulated to show case the gory aspect of African Traditional Religion and has successfully, submersed it with demonism which is at the detriment of its' associated values. The paper alludes that there are tremendous socio cultural values in African Traditional Religion that can be brought to the lime light through digital platform, while interfacing with the challenges of digitalization in Nigeria. The work recommends digital literacy and the teaching of African Traditional Religion all schools in the country. The paper deploys historical analyses research method. The scope of the work is Ayobo in Alimosho Local Government Area of Lagos State. While, David Harveys enlightenment theory is adopted for its theoretical framework.

Keywords: African Traditional Religion, Culture, Values, Digitalization and Contemporary Society

Introduction

African traditional religion is indigenous to the Africans. They are born and nurtured in it. A careful observation shows that Africans practice the religion rather than theorized it. Moreover, they are innately religious, the people hold on to the teachings and the practice of their religion, because it is highly pragmatic. Simply put, it is a problem solving religion. Significantly, the sum total of the life and the general activities of the Africans are largely interlaced with their religious tradition. Thus, for the Africans nothing happened by chance, every occurrence has a spiritual etiology and African indigenous religion is a tolerating and accommodating, its teachings are spread through oral tradition. The religion has a great deal of influence on the world view of the Africans. It is therefore an uphill task to comprehend the personality, philosophy and holistic outlook of an African without an in-depth knowledge of indigenous religion. Thus, Africans are notoriously religious.¹ Africans are incurably religious² and that Africans are reputedly religious³. Basically, Indigenous religion has no sacred text and it has no known founder like Islam, Christianity, and Buddhism etc.

Fundamentally, the religion hinges on the belief in the Supreme Being, the divinities, ancestors and other lesser spirits that resides in the groove, hill, forest, trees, animals, caves, shrine etc. As a matter of fact, the Africans belief and have the knowledge of the existence of a supreme deity before the invasion of the continent by the imperialist, that invaded the continent with various religious traditions from the west, Middle East and the Far East. As such it was a conclusive error for scholars like Emil Ludwig to have authoritatively declared thus, how can the untutored Africans conceive God? How can that be? Deity is a philosophical concept which salvage is incapable of comprehending.⁴ The intrusion and deliberate attempt to usurp African traditional religion by Africa invaders remains an attempt in futility, because despite the evangelistic tendencies of Islam

and Christianity in the Africa continent, indigenous religion is still very much alive among modern Africans. Imperatively, the belief in the existence of the divinities and the acknowledgment of the policing functions of deified ancestors provides a conscious link with which the Africans communicates with the supreme deity that is never dialyzed by the Africans. Africans have diverse channels to approach the supreme deity, because they perceived him to be too powerful and mighty and could destroy humanity at slightest provocation; however, they approach him direct in times of crisis and desperation. But the Africans feel safe and comfortable to reach the supreme deity through their ancestors who is conceived to be part of their family on earth despite their demise from the gross material world. The proximity of the ancestors to man, the effects of their sanctions as custodians of morality in the human society, prompted the Africans to be mindful of their daily conduct and general activities in relations to their family members and other persons in their community. The awareness of the present and watchful eyes of the ancestors in their community accounted for their enviable socio-cultural norms and values, inadvertently, this consciousness place the Africans on a unique cultural lane. These values require academic exposition, interrogation and evaluation.

Theoretical Framework

The paper adopts David Harvey's enlightenment theory, which is an 18th century European intellectual movement that swept away the parochial ideology and prejudice of the previous generation that were replaced with a more rational basis that accentuated a more robust social life. David Harvey a postmodernist commentator described the theory as an ideal that leveraged on the accumulation of knowledge generated by the aggregation of individuals that are working freely and innovatively pursue human emancipation, for the enrichment of daily life and advance development of humanity. The scientific domination of nature promised freedom from scarcity, want and the arbitrariness of natural calamity. The development of rationality form social organization and rational method of thinking, this liberated humanity from irrationality of myth, religion and superstition which led a release from the arbitrary use of power as well as from the dark side of our own human nature. The height of the age of enlightenment rested heavily on the French revolution of the 19th century.⁵

African tradition and culture has being jettisoned by many Africans who have comfortably settled for foreign culture and imbibe their values. The erosion of Africa values has birthed crisis, thus, Africans are bleeding from the pain of tribal animosity, ethnic tension, hatred, violence, poverty, political instability, injustice etc.⁶ Africa continent was invaded by new religion like Christianity, Islam and others, the infiltration of these religious traditions brought about religious plurality in the continent, unfortunately, the development led to tension, confusion, hatred, conflict and violence in a continent where people hitherto lived happily and peacefully. These Africa values need to be itemized, identified and restored, Africa must be taken back from western imperialist, it is only by so doing that she can break off from the shackles of neo colonialism, which is colonialism after colonialism.

The Values of African traditional Religion

The three recognize religions in Nigeria are Christianity, Islam and African traditional religion. Unfortunately, many Nigerians find it distasteful to associate with their indigenous religion, as a result of the influences of Christianity, Islam and globalization. However, they secretly consult diviners either physically or in prosy, particularly in times of crises and desperation, because African traditional religion is a pragmatic religion. Despite, effort by many Africans to separate themselves from the religion, it still reflect in their names, languages and culture. This is because, before their conversion to Christianity, they were Africans, who were deeply rooted in their religion before the intrusion of the migrating religion which is Islam and Christianity. The following are some of the values of African traditional religion.

1. **Marriage:** It is the union between a man and a woman that come together with the purpose of procreation, though, the union of human life is preserved, propagated and perpetuated⁷. Africans in their quest to westernized marriages, infused themselves with court, church and traditional or customary marriage, through which the groom pay the lawful bride price that actually, cement the union. The attempt by some Africans to organize court, church and traditional marriage is tantamount to socio-religious confusion and extravagancy, especially in a continent that is ravaged with the surge of pervasive poverty. The practice has come to stay, as a result of its socio acceptance, this ought not to be, particularly, because of its economic implication. It could account for why Africans place high premium on marriage much more than their western counter parts.
2. **Moral Values:** The belief in the existence of the ancestors and the fear of their sanctions; strengthen social legislation, that is enforced by the family, the formidable council of elders and the age grade. This moral checks help⁸ to guide the society against chaos and social confusion. Moreover, it promotes, friendship, love, honesty, justice, self-control, bravery, courage and compassion⁹ etc. Morality is embedded in various belief and customs that all Africans are expected to maintain, so as to enjoy life, good health and avoid curses. Meanwhile, immorality is strongly, discouraged among Africans, as a result of their belief in the ever watchful eyes of the ancestors. The efficacy of this belief system gives moral backing to justice, truth and the knowledge of the predominant effects of good and evil. Among Africans marriage is usually between two adult who must be of the opposite sex. Same sex marriage is strongly abhorred by the Africans. Moreover, the act of adultery among some Africans e.g, the Esan people of Edo central senatorial district usually attracts deadly sanction from the staple of the ever watchful ancestors.¹⁰
3. **Religious values of the Africans:** Religious leaders in African traditional religion are diviners, mediums; sorcerers, herbalist and soothsayers that have vast knowledge of the religion. They lead others during religious activities; they serve as a link between the people and the spiritual world. Some are trained while others are gifted, without them African religion would have disintegrated into chaos and confusion. As a matter of fact, they function as medicine men, healers and counselors. Their divine duties categories them as seers, diviners, mediums who officiate as ritual elders, that interprets is it gods or God's wishes to humanity. The awareness of their spiritual prowess by the Africans, streamline their behavioral disposition. The fear that any secret dealings an individual indulges will be revealed by these religious functionalities deterred the people from involving in criminal activities.
4. **Spiritual Communication:** Africans communicates with the supersensible world through prayers and divination, which is the practice of foretelling the future, reveal the unknown or find out the wish of a divinity or spirit.¹¹ African traditional religion and other religion(s) also create spiritual platform for gathering and group interaction either for worship, for sacrifice to the creator or for festivals.
5. **Spiritual Values;** African traditional religion brings about spiritual satisfaction. It nourishes the spiritual values, yearning and aspiration of man, because religion creates spiritual avenues for spiritual insight, development of man's psychic, prayers and give meaning to ritual, ceremonies, sacrifices, offerings, devotion, meditation, trust in God and so on. Moreover, religion enables man to quench his thirst for peace, joy, comfort, security, hope, love, progress, protection and self-awareness.¹²
6. **Aesthetic Values:** African aesthetic values are accentuated through their dressing, dance, religious symbols, festivals, etc. For instance, in Great Benin kingdom, the Egwie festival and their unique work of arts stand them out. These communicate about their culture and religion to the outside world. The aesthetic values of a society influences the artistes in his endeavour to produce acceptable aesthetic objects of immense values.¹³
7. **Philosophical Values of the Africans:** African religion enables man to be assertive of his origin, interpret the development of the world around him, express and explain mystical or cosmic phenomenon. This is of great significance to man, because the comprehension of the cosmogony affects their experience of life. It

is important to take into consideration, that religion supplies man answers to questions that bothered on reality.¹⁴ God's existence, destiny, reincarnation, suffering, pains, success, failure and eschatology.

8. **Africans treasure their religion:** Africans often protect their religion because of the values they placed on it; as such any threat against their religion is considered as a threat against their lives, culture and religious conviction. Hence, African traditional religion only fights against those that attack it.
9. **African traditional religion is the hall mark of Africa cultural identity:** Africa culture and religion are intertwined to an immeasurable extent, that the Africans are ready to render voluntary services in their course to promote the religion. Thus, they can inflict mark on their faces, bodies, deny themselves of pleasure, abandoned a lucrative carrier to serve as a religious functionary in the services of a deity. However odd this may seem, they are always elated about it.
10. **Value that the government placed on African traditional religion:** The constitution of many countries makes provision for the protection of the functionaries of various religions in their domain. It is for this reasons that the constitution pluralized religious worship in many states. Thus, the values the Osun and Lagos state government placed on African traditional religion. This manifested in the government declaration of Monday, August 22ND a yearly public holiday to mark the annual *Isele Day*, which is a traditional worshipper's day. The day is also known as *Odun Nla*, which means the peak of festivities among the adherents of traditional religion in South West Nigeria.¹⁵
11. **Acts of charity:** Africans are generously selfless; this is a virtue that is inculcated into them by their religion. They could sacrifice their hard earned resources for their religion, thus, they could build shrines or other sacred places of worship that are rich in traditional objects and treasures, as well as organize festivities to celebrate an aspect of their religion.
12. **Cultural Values:** It is extremely difficult to separate Africa cultural heritage from Africa religion. Hence, African traditional religion is laced with the culture of the Africans. This influences the totality of life of a group of believers, this influences starts from birth to death. For this remarkable reasons it is difficult to pull Africans out of their religious tradition, which is part and parcel of them, that is why Mbiti, concluded that Africans are notoriously religious.¹⁶
13. **Social Values of Religion:** African traditional religion is garnished with a lot of strings that enable Africans to celebrate life. This is expressed through drumming, shouting life and carrying out ceremonies, organized festivals and so on. Though, the religion provides an avenue that enable man to celebrate the sorrows and joy associated with existence¹⁷ the religion also galvanized the Africans to establish links with the spiritual spheres, through which the physical world is controlled. This shows the relationship between the physical and the spiritual world. A good example is the activities of diviners, the sanctions of the ancestors among Esan people of Edo State and so on.
14. **Sacrifice:** Africans are always ready to make sacrifice for their religion which could be their time, energy, fame, power, ambition, property and wealth. Thus, when the service of an individual is required by a deity, many of such individuals often abandon their pursuit for their religion. Although, there are instances of resistance, usually at the peril of the individual.¹⁸
15. **Taboos as social legislation:** Taboos are regarded as Awa by the Esan people and Eewo among the Yorubas. Taboos are custom or religion custom that prevent people from doing certain things or talk about some things in a particular way. In fact, taboos are unwritten laws that are used in guiding conducts, especially the youths from going against the wish of the community¹⁹. simply put, taboos are moral mystified, it faintly serves as social legislation, because it is put in place to maintain orders, rules and regulations in the society. It is still tenable till date. Two types of taboos are social and religious taboos.

Social taboos are social legislation that provided an ordered social life. Its violation might come with no consequences. For instance, it is a taboo for a woman to strip a child on her back while pounding yam, because the wrapper could lose and the child falls from her back.

Religious taboos are deeper than the social. It is put in place to give meaning or regards to custom and tradition. Its violation attracts dire consequences for the violator, the family and the community. No sane mind would dispute the essential of religious taboos to the continuity of the human society. For instance, it is a taboo to roast yam in the city, because, it pollutes the air and attract evil spirits. This could be responsible for the social disharmony we are experiencing today. Thus, ghastly motor accident and social violence are some of the consequences for the violation of this taboos.²⁰

16. **Divination:** The existence of man on earth is full of lots of uncertainties, regarding what the future hold in stock for him. The Africans consult diviners to find out about the future as well as to sort ways to deal with the teething problems around him, his family and community. As such, divination enables man to take charge of his life and family. Different ethnic groups in Africa relates with their ancestors through divination. Thus, the priests of the gods of iron-*Idigun*, the goddess of the sea-*Olokun*, who foretells the future when in spiritual ecstasy are all diviners.²¹
17. **Traditional Medicine:** Traditional medicine has proven to be efficacious in recent times; it should be well packaged to make it attractive. Traditional medicine experts should prepare it in tables, capsule and in bottles for sales to the public. After which it can be advertised on the social media.

African Traditional Religionists usually showcase their religion on the social media, however, it is just a few of them that do so, and this few are not generally accepted by the users/explorers of the media space, this can be attested to by their under footed comment that are laced with condemnation and calls for repentance. However other socially accepted aspect of the religion can be placed on the social media, while the aspect of animal sacrifice can be done secretly while, those that seeks for help can consult diviners behind close door. Christian and Muslim converts always attack the practitioners of ATR on the digital platform. After which they appeal to them to repent and give their life to Christ. But the practitioners of ATR are not perturbed as they know that the attack is all about lip service, as the same people that condemned and attack them in the day will certainly come and consult them at night, because ATR is problem solving religion.

Unpleasant Remarks of African Traditional Religion

African traditional religion has a lot of values that has tremendously impacted the lives of the Africans a great deal, which implies that the religion is highly prognostic, none evangelistic, but very empirical, which means, it is a problem solving religion. However, it has experience hot tongue lashes from armchair foreign observers who in a rather bias stance concluded that the religion is primitive, salvage, native, tribal, paganistic, heathen, fetish, animistic and idolatry²². Realistically, an insider view of the religion depicts monotheism, but heavily localized. Hence, different local settlements call upon the same God in different dialect. Fundamentally, Africans believe in God, the divinities, the ancestors, spirits, magic and medicine²³. Unfortunately, African traditional religion is a victim of western imperialism which has greatly diminished the religion. Painfully, Africans that find themselves in the mist of socio-economic and political turbulent will often consult diviners for solution to the problems that poses threat to their lives, but will go and share the testimony in their churches, what a deception, confusion and self-delusion. The continuous demonization of African traditional religion is inimical to the religion. This has done the religion more harm than good, the coming of the Portuguese missionaries to Africa and the subsequent conversion of the Africans to Christianity has led to spiritual confrontation rather than identification with some of the values that are provided by African indigenous religion.

Digitalization

Digitalization is the use of digital technology and probably digitalized information to create and harvest values in new ways.²⁴It could also mean the way many domains of social life are restructured around digital communication and media infrastructure. In simple terms, digitalization is the use of digital technologies.²⁵ It could also mean the transformation all information type (text, sound, visuals, video and other from various

sources) into digital language.²⁶ Digital platform is supposed to be used to promote Africa culture and tradition. Unfortunately, the reversed is the case. It is rather appropriated to damage and to malign the religion, to the extent that it is now labeled as a demonic religion, it now appears as if there is nothing worthy about the religion. These negative vibes are propagated by born again Pentecostal Christians, pastors, evangelist and even Muslims, that are of the view that the adherents of African traditional religion have relationship with the devil, because the religion is characterized with the worship of deified ancestors who are supposed to be left to rest in peace. Their post in the social media is embellished with the condemnation of the religion, its functionaries and followers.

Thus, Gerrie Terhaar and Stephen Ellis stated that what we learn in the social media regarding African traditional religion and its functionaries throughout west, central, and southern Africa are news of people being killed by politicians and business men who used their body parts through the assistance of diviners to prepare powerful medicines that will enable them to achieve material success.²⁷ There are television soap opera, home video, radio program and phone in, in Africa that dramatizes stories of witches, frightful ghost, spirits and ritual wealth.²⁸ The social media platform is use to showcase diviners that called out to people to come for ritual wealth. Moreover, it is also used to publicize how people get wealthy by exchanging their manhood and womb for spiritual wealth and later become impotent and barren. Some people could even exchange their children for riches; the child could later become an imbecile, sick or even die.

Many Nigeria home videos like living in bondage capture a story line that centered on Andy an upcoming businessman, who exchanged the life of his newly married wife for wealth, but the wealth started to diminish, after his mother-in-law went to cry on her daughter's grave side, asking her daughter to avenge her death.²⁹ It was posted recently that a native doctor in Onitsha, Anambra state impregnated a pastors wife, who has being barren for many years. The incident occurred when the pastor's wife went to seek spiritual help from the diver who was identified as Ekwe-Baba.³⁰ In a related development, pastors go to diviners to prepare charms that they use to populate their churches; some could even go as far as having intercourse with their daughter and use a handkerchief to clean the fluids that is waved in the church for the demonstration of extraordinary power.³¹ A girl that was possess of witchcraft powers was delivered by a new generation Pentecostal pastor in the presence of a hundred of worshippers during deliverance service, it was reported that she vomited a live snake.³²

These stories are carefully crafted to demonized and reduce African traditional religion to the background, despite its numerous embracing values. A rational observation shows that the report in the social media aimed at promoting new Pentecostal pastors and their churches at the detriment of Africa traditional religion. These have really reduced the religion a great deal. However, there are unethical practices within the religion, but not exclusive to African traditional religion. It is therefore a fallacy of hasty generalization to use the behavior of a few unethical practices of some diviners to evaluate African traditional religion. This should not be accepted because it is a conclusion in error.

Ways to Use Digital Technology to Promote African Traditional Religion

1. Practitioners and adherents of the religion can leverage on television, print media and social media to promote the teachings and values of the religion, for instance, these could popularized Africa medicine and divination. But a situation where functionaries of the religion are only seen and not heard will continuously place the religion at the background. This is the current situation of the religion.
2. People that have benefitted from the provision and values of the religion should speak out. So that others that have related issues could come to diviners for solution. This will help to promote the religion, within and outside Africa.
3. Values of the religion should be documented for the benefit of the coming generation as well for the clarification of issues that require explanation.

Challenges of Digitalization in Nigeria

The digital platform has triggered socio-economic and political transformation in Nigeria. It is therefore expedient for religious leaders and their adherents to master the handling of digital technology. However, there are challenges which include the following:

1. **Illiteracy:** The literacy level of Nigerians and Africans in general is very low, particularly among rural dwellers, who are the major functionaries of the religion. These set of people find it difficult to use technology. Ironically, the harnessing of the provision of technology is very important at this material time.
2. **Network failure:** In most cases there are no network coverage in some places, while there are no mask mounted in some parts, accessing social media become extremely impossible.
3. **Financial challenges:** The poverty level in Nigeria is very huge, survival is of the fittest, Many Nigerians are struggling with the provision of shelter, clothes and food and care less about data to access the internet.
4. **Epileptic power supply:** Power supply in Nigeria is still at its abysmal level, where there is no power to charge computers, iPod, or hand set, the gadgets would be powerless and deformed, hence, cannot be put to use.
5. **High rate unemployment:** Nigeria is smolder with unemployment; as such many Nigerians cannot afford phones that are internet compliance, for instance, Iphone and Androids.
6. **Misinformation:** Recently digital platform is used by dubious people to disseminate fake news and content that nail African traditional religion to the dust bin of history, this has so affected African traditional religion that Africans have developed thick hatred for the religion and would not want to associate with it. This ought not to be, as it is expected that the religious space and faith of others should be respected and tolerated.

Recommendations

1. Cyber engineers should put mechanism in place to regulate information in the digital space, so that post that depicts religious intolerance and promote bad blood amongst adherents of various religions can be pull down immediately.
2. Education should be accessible by all citizens, through it, they will be trained on how to use digital technology. This will improved on the quality of life of the people.
3. Practitioners of Africa traditional religion, should stop living in the past and harness on the provision of digital technology to promote, preach and spread the religion all over Nigeria in particular and Africa in general.
4. Government should implement policies that will bring about rapid economic development that will lead to the employment of majority of the citizens so as to empower them financially.
5. The teaching of African traditional religion as a matter of urgency, must be introduced at all level of education in Nigeria.

Conclusion

Religion plays an extensive function in the society that is why man places a lot of importance on it, to the extent that he is ready to die for the course of his religion. The Africans are born into the religion of their forebears, a practical religion that tolerates other religion at its detriment. This is what Islam and Christianity capitalized on, that they started a rigorous campaign against African traditional religion. They deplore all their artilleries against a religion that appears to be less concern, the pressure is so strong that Africans now find it difficult to associate with the religion through which they express their cultural heritage and inherited values. Notwithstanding the pressure from Islam and Christianity, the factor of education played a formidable role against Africa culture and religion, as such Africans had problems of documentation and this has affected Africans a great deal. Africans should be proud of their religion and tap into the potentials provided by their religion.

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